

Supplementary information to “THE ANATOMY OF EIGHTEENTH CENTURY COLLECTIONS ONLINE (ECCO)”

Definition of the publication format categories used in the article

A precise definition of an eighteenth-century pamphlet or book is impossible. According to Halasz (1997: 3), “neither "pamphlet" nor "book" is a generic category, but rather, an indicator of object form that slides easily into commodity designation (and dismissal) ... "pamphlet" functions as a floating signifier in the heterogeneity that characterizes the opportunities made available by print”. Indeed, pamphlets (as well as books) are often used as an intuitive category. For example, in Wiley’s *Companion to the History of the Book* (that has 975 pages), pamphlet(s) is referred to 63 times without an exact attempt to define it.

Where a concrete definition has been required, it is often based on page counts. For example, UNESCO has used 48 pages as the cutoff point between pamphlets and books. According to Raymond (2003: 81-82) on the other hand, early modern book trade actors conceived a pamphlet as anything that could be roughly stitched together rather than thoroughly sewn. From limits mentioned in multiple early modern agreements and acts, she ends up with a definition of a pamphlet having at most 96 pages. However, she also makes the point (2003: 7) that by the eighteenth century, “pamphlet” was a useful word but its definition had been blurred (also because of the popularity of octavo and duodecimo formats).

Fig. A1 ECCO coverage increases with page count, and varies by document format.

Based on the above, our interest here too is not a general definition of a pamphlet as such, but to arrive at a practical definition which can act as convenient short-hand for noticing differences in how publications of different types behave in the data. Thus, while we did want our definitions to align with common understanding, we also wanted the data to inform where we placed our precise cutoffs. After multiple experiments, we decided to set our cut-off for pamphlets at 32 pages. As shown in Figure A1, this is a point in the data where qualitative changes in ECCO coverage synchronize between different gathering types, even if the nature of those changes differs by gathering type. First, for octavo and quarto pages, up until 32 pages, every doubling of page count increases a book's chance of making it into ECCO approximately by 10 percentage points. In other words, the shorter the pamphlet-sized work, the less likely it is to be included in ECCO. For folio gatherings, on the other hand, 32 pages is instead the point where coverage starts to rise. Duodecimo acts in a slightly more complicated manner, with a plateau in coverage appearing already between 16 and 32 pages, but then coverage rises again between 32 and 64 pages. Still, here too 32 marks a change in behaviour.

A further reason for setting the limit for pamphlets as low as 32 is that this way, we can be quite sure that all publications belonging to this category really were thought of as pamphlets, before we venture into an area where there could be more doubt as to the nature of the publication. On the same basis of trying to ensure clear end-categories, we decided to use 128 pages as the cutoff point for books, the point at which we felt comfortable thinking all publications to represent a full-length book. With these definitions, in between the two categories are left all

books between 33 and 127 pages in length.

Defined this way, pamphlets make up 50% of the ESTC for the whole of the 18th century, while books and in-between works each make up 25%. Further, these percentages stay remarkably constant through time, even while total volume increases drastically after 1780.

While we have made our analyses based on all three of these categories, in the article we will always present results for the pamphlets and books only, leaving out the category of in-between. This is done in the interest of clarity of presentation, as in behaviour, the category of in-between works follows that of the category of books, but is less distinct due to bleed-through from both other categories.

As an aside, in Figure A1 about the page count and ECCO coverage, we also notice interesting developments in itself. First, octavo and quarto documents follow a very similar curve. It is even more interesting that duodecimo documents divert from this curve and for example, the coverage of 24-page duodecimo documents compared to quarto works with similar page count is considerably lower. Only when reaching mid-range and book-length does the coverage of duodecimo documents approaches octavo and quarto size coverage. And, what is most noticeable is the lowest coverage of folio documents, especially with respect to pamphlet-sized products where the coverage remains under 30% in ECCO. Only the larger books over 256 pages have a >60% coverage.

Description and evaluation of the method used for subject topic analysis

Evaluating whether ECCO covers different subjects equally is difficult. First, ESTC, against which we need to compare, uses the Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH). These are rather detailed, with altogether 9,425 distinct subject headings referenced in our data. Because the LCSH does not contain aggregating hierarchies, these cannot be easily combined to larger thematic categories. To get around this, we use the information we have from ECCO, which categorises all its records into eight categories: Fine Arts, General Reference, History and Geography, Law, Literature and Language, Medicine, Science and Technology, Religion and Philosophy and Social Sciences. By going through each ECCO book, and tabulating the LC subject headings associated with them, we can obtain mappings from the subject headings to each of the eight categories.

However, even before we get to this point, we needed to evaluate the ECCO categorization itself. Naturally, the categorization of a century of books into eight general categories can never be fully accurate and it is difficult to know which category some works belong to. Thus, to evaluate the usability of these categorizations for analysis, we randomly sampled 20 publications for each subject topic/publication format combination, resulting in a total of 160 entries. Overall, the random sampling revealed that most of the categories are surprisingly accurate except for General Reference. Also, there is some overlap between History and

Geography and Social Sciences, but much less than what we anticipated given the difficulty of classifying social sciences in the eighteenth century.

Based on the evaluation of the categorization, we went forward with the mapping task. By calculating how often each LC subject heading is associated with each of the eight categories, we obtained a total of 14,082 mappings for the 7,329 LC headings appearing in ECCO material. Although the two classification schemes may have different design principles and hence only partial overlap, we anticipated that many of the categories have unambiguous correspondence. To quantify this, we associated each of these mappings with a number depicting the exclusivity of the association, calculated as the percentage of works with a given LC heading associated with that particular ECCO category. Thresholding based on this measure, we can balance mapping coverage against mapping accuracy.

Fig. A2 Relationship between coverage and accuracy of subject categorization as a function of the mapping threshold.

To evaluate approximate accuracy, we measured for ECCO the agreement percentage between projected categories and actual gold standard categories for each threshold. As seen in Figure A2, an inverse linear relationship is evident between accuracy and coverage. As we raise the requirement for the exclusivity of the association between an LC subject heading and its predicted category, we obtain better classification accuracies, but our expanded categorisation covers a much smaller part of the 18th-century ESTC. At one end, we obtain a near 100% accuracy, but can extend our categorisation to only 20% of the ESTC. At the other end, our accuracy drops to only 50%, but we are able to cover almost 60% of the ESTC, which is actually the maximum possible, as only that proportion of the 18th century ESTC has any LCSH headings at all. Further, it must be noted that there is a distinct effect where between books, in-betweens

and pamphlets, books are consistently both the best covered, as well as best mapped at a particular threshold.

Fig. A3 A confusion matrix showing, in percents, the gold standard composition of each of our reconstructed categories for different thresholds between 0.1 and 0.9.

After looking at the general behaviour of the mapping accuracy across publication formats and thresholds, we also wanted to evaluate whether the expansion treated the different categories differently. Thus, we calculated a confusion matrix for each category and threshold. From this matrix (visualized in Figure A3), we decided that for our analyses, The Fine Arts, History and Geography and General Reference categories could not be used due to their mappings being unreliable (often ending up within Literary and Language). Further, we saw that the categories of Law and Social Sciences were often being confused with each other, so merged them in our analysis.

Reasoning for being able to use Gale's OCR engine confidence values as estimates of OCR quality

In earlier work (Hill & Hengchen 2019) comparing the ECCO-TCP hand-transcribed subset of ECCO1 to the OCR'd version, we identified that on an overall level, the token-level mean precision of OCR in this ECCO subset was 0.744 (meaning that on average, 74% of the tokens in ECCO OCR are correct), with recall being 0.814 (meaning that 81% of the tokens in the original are included in the OCR'd version).

While these benchmarking results apply only to the small manually curated ECCO-TCP subset, a much larger number of quality scores is available as OCR engine confidence values in the Gale OCR. We identified a statistically significant ($P < 0.001$) Pearson correlation of 0.795 between the manually curated page-level F1 scores (the harmonic mean of precision and recall) and the automated OCR engine confidence values reported in the Gale OCR data. This agreement with the manually curated subset indicates that the more widely available OCR engine confidence values can be used as a proxy to accurately assess OCR quality also beyond the small hand-curated subset.

However, it must also be noted that ECCO1 and ECCO2 arise from different OCR processes, and the above correlation strictly applies only to ECCO1 due to the ECCO-TCP only containing material from it. Yet, the confidence scores for both ECCO1 and ECCO2 do follow similar patterns concerning time, language and other secondary axes, suggesting that also the ECCO2 engine confidence could be trusted.